

NAAC Revised Assessment and Accreditation Process at a Glance

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ABSTRACT

Recently the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) have revised the Assessment and Accreditation Process launched in July 2017. The Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) will now be assessed with the new process whose online submission has started from 9th November 2017. The new process represents an explicit paradigm shift making it ICT enabled, objective, transparent, scalable and robust.

Since the process is going to be implemented first time, many institutes are facing many queries to comply with the mandatory requirements of NAAC. The Research paper attempts to address the above issue and provide a glance of the Revised Assessment and Accreditation Process thereby by guiding the institutes to apply for NAAC at an ease.

Keywords: NAAC, Assessment, Accreditation, Framework

1. Introduction:

In view with the changing trends in higher education and aligning the reforms and rapidly transforming global education scenario, NAAC has embarked in revising the Assessment and Accreditation (A&A) methodology. Accordingly the Revised Assessment and Accreditation (A&A) Framework was launched in July 2017. Let us take a glance of the revised process.

2. Revised Assessment and Accreditation Framework:

The Revised process is an explicit paradigm shift from earlier process making it ICT enabled, objective, transparent, scalable and robust. The shift is:

- from qualitative peer judgement to data based quantitative indicator evaluation with increased objectivity and transparency
- towards extensive use of ICT confirming scalability and robustness
- in terms of simplification of the process drastic reduction in number of questions, size of the report, visit days, and so on
- In terms of boosting benchmarking as quality improvement tool. This has been attempted through comparison of NAAC indicators with other international QA frameworks
- Introducing pre-qualifier for peer team visit, as 30% of system generated score.
- Introducing *System Generated Scores* (SGS) with combination of online evaluation (about 70%) and peer judgement (about 30%)
- in introducing the element of *third party validation* of data
- in providing appropriate differences in the metrics, weightages and benchmarks to universities, autonomous colleges and affiliated/constituent colleges
- in revising several metrics to bring in enhanced participation of students and alumni in the assessment process

3. Criteria for Assessment

NAAC has identified the following seven criteria to serve as the basis of its assessment procedures:

1. Curricular Aspects
2. Teaching-Learning and Evaluation
3. Research, Innovations and Extension
4. Infrastructure and Learning Resources
5. Student Support and Progression
6. Governance, Leadership and Management
7. Institutional Values and Best Practices

3.1 Key Indicators

Under each Criterion a few Key Indicators are identified. These Key Indicators (KIs) are further delineated as Metrics which actually elicit responses from the HEIs. Distribution of Weightages across 7 Criteria and 34 Key Indicators (KIs) is as follows:

Criteria	Key Indicators (KIs)	Universities	Autonomous Colleges	Affiliated Colleges
1. Curricular Aspects	1.1 *(U) Curriculum Design and Development	50	50	NA
	*(A) Curricular Planning and Implementation	NA	NA	20
	1.2 Academic Flexibility	50	40	30
	1.3 Curriculum Enrichment	30	40	30
	1.4 Feedback System	20	20	20
	Total	150	150	100
2. Teaching-Learning and Evaluation	2.1 Student Enrolment and Profile	10	20	30
	2.2 Catering to Student Diversity	20	30	50
	2.3 Teaching-Learning Process	20	50	50
	2.4 Teacher Profile and Quality	50	60	80
	2.5 Evaluation Process and Reforms	40	40	50
	2.6 Student Performance and Learning Outcomes	30	50	40
	2.7 Student satisfaction Survey	30	50	50
	Total	200	300	350
3. Research, Innovations and Extension	3.1 Promotion of Research and Facilities	20	20	NA
	3.2 Resource Mobilization for Research	20	10	10
	3.3 Innovation Ecosystem	30	20	10
	3.4 Research Publications and Awards	100	20	20
	3.5 Consultancy	20	10	NA
	3.6 Extension Activities	40	50	60
	3.7 Collaboration	20	20	20
	Total	250	150	120

4. Infrastructure and Learning Resources	4.1 Physical Facilities	30	30	30
	4.2 Library as a Learning Resource	20	20	20
	4.3 IT Infrastructure	30	30	30
	4.4 Maintenance of Campus Infrastructure	20	20	20
	Total	100	100	100
5. Student Support and Progression	5.1 Student Support	30	30	50
	5.2 Student Progression	40	30	45
	5.3 Student Participation and Activities	20	30	25
	5.4 Alumni Engagement	10	10	10
	Total	100	100	130
6. Governance, Leadership and Management	6.1 Institutional Vision and Leadership	10	10	10
	6.2 Strategy Development and Deployment	10	10	10
	6.3 Faculty Empowerment Strategies	30	30	30
	6.4 Financial Management and Resource Mobilization	20	20	20
	6.5 Internal Quality Assurance System	30	30	30
	Total	100	100	100
7. Institutional Values and Best Practices	7.1 Institutional Values and Social Responsibilities	50	50	50
	7.2 Best Practices	30	30	30
	7.3 Institutional Distinctiveness	20	20	20
	Total	100	100	100
	TOTAL SCORE	1000	1000	1000

*(U) - applicable only for Universities and Autonomous Colleges

(A) - applicable only for the Affiliated / Constituent Colleges

NA - Not Applicable

Table 1: Distribution of Weightages across 7 Criteria and 34 Key Indicators (KIs)

4. Revised Assessment and Accreditation Process of NAAC

* Main Process Components – normal path

Fig 1: NAAC A&A Process*

Fig 2: Institutional Information for Quality Assessment (IIQA) Application Process

Fig 3: SSR Application and Assessment

5. The Grading Pattern – Introduction of Grade Qualifiers

The revised framework will be more ICT intensive and ‘outcome based’. The current grading pattern of NAAC (A++, A+, A, B++, B+, B, C, D) would be continued for accreditation.

CGPA	Letter Grade	Status
3.51 – 4.00	A++	Accredited
3.26 – 3.50	A+	Accredited
3.01 – 3.25	A	Accredited
2.76 – 3.00	B++	Accredited
2.51 – 2.75	B+	Accredited
2.01 – 2.50	B	Accredited
1.51 – 2.00	C	Accredited
≤ 1.50	D	Not Accredited

Table 2: Grading System

A system of applying minimum qualifiers for achieving a grade has been designed and will be implemented. For eg. Universities should score a minimum of 3.01 in Criteria 1, 2 and 3 for achieving a “A” “A+” “A++” grade

Fig 4: Grading and Accreditation

6. Benefits of Accreditation

Accreditation facilitates

- Institution to know its strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities through an informed review process.
- Identification of internal areas of planning and resource allocation
- Collegiality on the campus.
- Funding agencies look for objective data for performance funding.
- Institutions to initiate innovative and modern methods of pedagogy.
- New sense of direction and identity for institutions.
- The society look for reliable information on quality education offered.
- Employers look for reliable information on the quality of education offered to the prospective recruits.
- Intra and inter-institutional interactions.

7. Conclusion

The Revised NAAC process is a paradigm shift from earlier process making it ICT enabled, objective, transparent, scalable and robust. However if the points mentioned in the research paper are gone thoroughly will definitely ease on the process for the HEIs.

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